

TECHNOLOGY OF PEELING AND DRYING OF FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

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Abstract. *Fruits and vegetables are separated into primary and secondary mass, cleaned, freeze-dried and ground into powder using a grinding machine. By dyeing various clothes, fabrics and thread products in the garment and textile industry, the secondary mass of the product with color properties can be used to reduce the cost of finished products by approximately 1-1.5 times.*

Keywords: *primary and secondary mass, peel, freezing, powder, organoleptic.*

Today, the development of ecologically pure natural food production technology is considered to be of great importance. To eliminate these issues, the priority goal is to reduce the cost of products in domestic and foreign markets by expanding the range of fruit and vegetable processing technology. I believe that it is appropriate to use the primary and secondary products released by peeling fruits and vegetables in various industrial production enterprises.

Storage and processing of agricultural products is considered one of the urgent issues today. To dry fruits and vegetables, to evaporate the amount of moisture contained in the product, by drying fruits and vegetables by peeling them from their skin (peeling), by producing a wide range of products from primary and secondary raw materials, products with high quality indicators are obtained for consumers.

The following functional tasks are achieved by peeling and drying fruits and vegetables.

When drying fruits and vegetables by peeling their skins, organoleptic parameters (shape, size, taste, color and smell), shape and content of active vitamins were preserved;

By peeling and freezing fruits and vegetables, it was possible to reduce the drying time of products by 2-3 times;

- A technology for the production of children's ingredients was created by peeling and freezing fruits and vegetables;

- The technology of obtaining natural dyes from powders prepared through the primary and secondary mass of fruits and vegetables was created;

- "Tannin substance" was isolated from fruits (palms) as a secondary product (pod);

- The assortment of tourism and export products from the products obtained by drying fruits and vegetables has been improved;

- He succeeded in creating the technology of obtaining natural color dyes from product samples taken from raw materials to production enterprises;

- The technology for the production of nutritional additives for powder flour and bread products prepared by drying fruits and vegetables was created;

- A wide range of functional food products are also produced from primary and secondary products. Today, the processing of fruits and vegetables, that is, drying, causes some difficulties, that is, due to the hardness of the skin part of some products, it takes a long time to dry the existing moisture in the product under the influence of heat. In order to overcome these problems, the drying period of fruits and vegetables is reduced by peeling off the skin, it is possible to obtain an

ecologically pure product, and the energy-saving feature increases and it brings high economic efficiency.

A technological scheme for the production of functional products by separating the primary and secondary mass of products through the scheme presented below.

It is presented in Fig 1.

Figure 1. Technological scheme of peeling and drying fruits and vegetables
The range of products obtained by drying the primary and secondary mass of fruits and vegetables is presented in Fig 2.

Figure 2. Assortment of products obtained by drying fruits and vegetables from their primary and secondary skins.

Fruits and vegetables are separated into primary and secondary mass, cleaned, freeze-dried and ground into powder using a grinding machine. The secondary mass of the product with color properties is used to reduce the cost of finished products by dyeing various clothes, fabrics and thread products in the garment and textile industry. In the food industry, as a result of its use in various natural drinks, concentrates and bakery products, confectionary and confectionary products, it is possible to increase the range of products with high organoleptic indicators and reduce the cost of finished and semi-finished products in stores and stalls.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that by drying fruits and vegetables from their primary and secondary mass without perishing, the nutritional value of products increases, as a result, the range of natural pure drinks, children's ingredients and confectionery products is increased and the next generation is provided with a healthy lifestyle.

REFERENCES

1. Meliboev M.F., Mamatov Sh.M., Ergashev O.K. Razrabotka kombinirovannogo metoda sublimatsionnoy i dielektricheskoy sushki // Universum: texnicheskie nauki. – Moskva-2022. - №5 (98). – S.5-8
2. Meliboev M.F., Mamatov Sh.M., Ergashev O.K. Energopotreblenie i ekonomicheskie pokazateli pri sublimatsionnoy i mikrovolnovoy sublimatsionnoy sushke sliv // Universum: texnicheskie nauki. – Moskva-2022. - №5 (98). – S.9-12

3. Meliboyev M.M., Mamatov Sh.M., Ergashev O.K. The use of dielectric waves in sublimation drying equipment and the effect of the combined drying method on the drying period // Scientific and technical magazine of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology. - 2021.-№3.- 79-84 b.
4. Mamatov Sh.M., Aripov M., Meliboyev M., Shamsutdinov B. Advantages of quick-freezing technology of cherry// International journal of innovative technology and exploring engineering (IJITEE) (Indian). 2020. - №9(3) 2278-3075. - pp. 3254-3256. (8917.019320)
5. M.F. Meliboyev. Olxo'rini quritishda yuqori samarador kombinatsion usullardan foydalanish. Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori dissertatsiyasi, - Toshkent: TKTI, 2022 y., 104 b.
6. Saribaeva Dilorom Akramzhanovna, Zokirova Mashkhura Sodikzhanovna Study of the elemental and amino acid composition of ginger extract // Universum: technical sciences. 2021. No. 11-3 (92). (Date of access: 11/03/2022).
7. Saribaeva Dilorom, Zokirova Mashxura, Kholdarova Gulsanam Researching the technology of making beverages of containing fruit juice // Universum: technical sciences. 2022. No. 1-3 (94).URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/researching-the-technology-of-making-beverages-of-containing-fruit-juice> (Date of access: 03.11.2022).
8. Sarybayeva Dilorom Akramzhanovna, Holdarova Gulsanam Akramjon Kizi. Research of the processes of obtaining functional beverages based on milk thistle extract (SILYBUM MARIANUM L.) // Universum: technical sciences. 2022. №11-4 (104). (accessed: 23.12.2022).
9. Meliboyev M.M., Mamatov Sh.M., Ergashev O.K. The use of dielectric waves in sublimation drying equipment and the effect of the combined drying method on the drying period // Namangan muhandislik-texnologiya instituti ilmiy-texnika jurnali. - 2021.-№3.- 79-84 b. (05.00.00, №33)
10. Meliboyev M.M. Impact of the combined drying method on the drying object and economic analysis of the organoleptic characteristics of the dried product// Namangan muhandislik-texnologiya instituti ilmiy-texnika jurnali. 2021.-№3.- 97-101b. (05.00.00., №33)
11. Meliboyev M.M., Mamatov Sh.M., Ergashev O.K. Mevalarni energiyatejamkor vakuum-sublimatsion quritish qurilmasida dielektrik mikroto'lqinlardan foydalanib quritish // Namangan davlat universiteti ilmiy-axborotnomasi. 2021.-№2.- 46-52b. (02.00.00, №18)